

COMPLIMENTS IN THE ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES, LINGUOCULTURAL ANALYSIS

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Annotatsiya. Tadqiqot ishining maqsadi- iltifot misolidagi nutq harakatlarining lingvomadaniy xususiyatlarini aniqlashdan iborat. Tadqiqot jarayonida iltifot nutq harakatlarini ifodalash vositalarini tahlil qilishga asosiy urg'u beriladi, iltifotning asosiy shakllari va turlarini aniqlash ham shular jumlasidandir. Bundan tashqari, muallif iltifotning nutq odobi va nutq harakatlaridagi o`rnini, iltifot ko`rsatuvchi va qabul qiluvchilarning rus va ingliz lingvomadaniyatlaridagi niyatlarini ham belgilaydi.

Kalit so`zlar: nutqiy aktlar, iltifot, maqtoq, iltifotni qabul qiluvchi, madaniyatlararo muloqot, til diskursi, lingvomadaniy tahlil.

Аннотация. Целью работы является определение лингвокультурных особенностей русского и английского речевого акта, такого как комплимент. В ходе исследования основная роль отводится анализу средств выражения речевых актов комплимента; выявлению основных форм и видов комплимента. Кроме того автор определяет место комплимента в речевом этикете и речевом поведении, реципиенты и адресаты комплимента и их намерения в русской и английской лингвокультурах.

Ключевые слова: Речевые акты, комплимент, похвала, адресат, межкультурная коммуникация, языковой дискурс, лингвокультурологический анализ.

Abstract. It aims at determining the linguistic and cultural characteristics of Russian and English speech act such as a compliment. In the course of the study the main role is dedicated to the analysis of the means of expression of compliment speech acts; identification of the main forms and types of compliment. Moreover, the author determines the place of compliment in speech etiquette and speech behaviour, recipients and addressees of the compliment and their intentions in Russian and English linguistic cultures.

Key words: Speech acts, compliment, praise, addressee, intercultural communication, linguistic discourse, linguocultural analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Compliment in the English and Russian communicative cultures investigated in this work in line with the theory of speech acts. The consideration of speech acts originated in the field of analytical philosophy, after which it took shape in a separate linguistic direction in order to find the relationship of language with objects of the world [4.166].

In physiological terms, a speech act is performed in the process of pronouncing sounds and writing letters designating them. However, significant differences are revealed between the simple utterance of sounds/spelling of letters and the performance of a speech act. One of the main differences is that a speech act is possible only when the combination of sounds or letters matters. A simple set of sounds that does not matter will not be considered a speech act. Therefore, each chain of morphemes produced by a person in a speech act always matters [11.162].

According to D.F. Komorova, the concept of "speech act" should be approached from the point of view of pragmatics, according to which a speech act is a "speech action that is carried out by the speaker in order to express hope for a certain state of affairs in the life of the

addressee in the future in order to inform him about the speaker's assessment of the properties or actions of the addressee or the situation as a whole" [6, 20].

Among the main characteristics of a speech act, intentionality stands out, i.e. intent, purposefulness, conventionality, correlation with the speaker's face and sequence [1. 688].

LITERATURE REVIEW

A compliment as one of the attributes of speech behaviour attracts the attention of many researchers. At present, studies from various fields of humanitarian knowledge are devoted to the study of compliment: pragmatics, linguodidactics, linguistics, cultural studies, text theory, rhetoric, sociology (N.N. Germanova, O.S. Issers, V.I. Karasik, V.V. Leontyev, I.S. Morozova, E.S. Petelina and others).

METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

The methodological basis of the study was the works in the field of:

- theories of speech acts (N.D. Arutyunova, G.P. Grice, D. Davidson, J. Austin, E.V. Paducheva, J. Searle, V.N. Telia and others);
- linguistic, cultural and intercultural communication (L.G. Vedenina, E.M. Wolf, I.M. Kobozeva, V.A. Maslova, E.V. Paducheva, V.N. Telia, S.G. Ter-Minasova, N.I. Formanovskaya and others);
- gender linguistics (E.I. Goroshko, A.V. Kirilina, V.V. Leontiev, E. Mitrokhina, I.S. Morozov).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In modern linguistics and philology, compliment is considered not only in the framework of the theory of speech acts, but also as a component of speech etiquette and speech behavior of people in the framework of interpersonal communication. Etiquette in the general sense of the word means "rules of good form; the accepted order of conduct, providing contact and maintaining respectful, friendly communication of interlocutors in various situations".

The connection between compliment and speech etiquette in Russian linguistics was first revealed by N. I. Formanovskaya. From her point of view, speech etiquette should be understood as "a microsystem of nationally specific sustainable communication formulas adopted and prescribed by society to establish contact between interlocutors, maintain communication in a chosen key" [12.295].

Politeness as a special category of a communicative speech act is distinguished due to the fact that it is designed to regulate the communicative effect of interlocutors, prescribe the norms of both verbal and non-verbal behavior of people in the process of communication, and also regulate the relationship of people in interpersonal group or mass communication, in which compliment is of no small importance. The compliment in the framework of speech etiquette is standardized and official. Consequently, normalized complementary formulas characteristic of a certain time period and a specific country are used in speech behavior.

A compliment as a component of speech etiquette and speech summarization is related to the category of politeness. Politeness is understood as "the central and fundamental category of communicative consciousness, the content of which is, on the one hand, a set of standardized norms and rules of social behavior that govern the communicative interaction of communicating, on the other hand, a system of communicative strategies of positive and negative politeness aimed at harmonious, conflict-free communication" [2. 45].

A compliment as a form of speech etiquette has significant differences in English and Russian cultures. A distinctive feature of a compliment when comparing speech etiquette from different countries and cultures is the difference in the expression of compliment and its

assessment in English and Russian communicative cultures. Among the main differences between the English and Russian compliments in this chapter highlighted are: • The importance of a compliment in communication.

In different communicative situations, representatives of the English-speaking nation often and repeatedly use evaluative cues. Such hyperbolization of the British leads to the fact that representatives of other cultures (including Russian linguistic culture) consider such compliments insincere, i.e. doubt the veracity of the pleasant words of the British [7. 132-137].

In English culture, compliments are used much more often than in Russian culture, since English culture is characterized by exaggeration in expressing ratings. Russian people are much less likely to use compliments in speech. This is due to the fact that in their national character, Russians have straightforward behavior. Their assessments are always sincere, even if such an assessment may offend the interlocutor. Consequently, the Russian communicative culture is characterized, first of all, by the fact that compliment takes an insignificant place here [9. 193].

Orientation to a certain style of communication. In Russian culture, compliment is a status-oriented style, while in English culture, compliment is a personality-oriented style of communication. The Russian communication style in this speech act is considered a status-oriented style, which is most clearly expressed in the use of the pronouns “you” and “you” in different communication situations. If we compare this feature with the English linguistic culture, in particular, here we can distinguish personality-oriented communication style as opposed to the Russian status-oriented style. A personality-oriented style of communication involves a more informal communication between English-speaking people, symmetrical relationships between interlocutors, with the emphasis in the process of communication being on their equality [3. 20].

Differences in the compliment speech act in Russian and English are also in the thematic aspect. While Russian people more often pay attention to external factors and a person’s professionalism during a complimentary speech act, in English culture, on the contrary, a person’s internal, moral qualities and mental abilities are more likely to be complimented [8. 58].

In English linguistic culture, compliment is a rational speech act. In Russian culture, the degree of emotionality of a compliment is much higher. Unlike Russian linguistic culture, the British often use rational compliments as opposed to emotional ones, which are more characteristic, in this comparison, of Russian linguistic culture. The ability of a Russian person to display a wide range of emotions and feelings is defined by the Russian linguistic consciousness as a moral quality associated with the attitude to other people [5. 32].

In English communicative culture, the response to a compliment is more often positive or neutral. In Russian linguistic culture, a negative reaction of the interlocutor is characteristic, which is not accepted in English-speaking countries. In Russian-language communication, a negative response to a compliment is more frequent, which can occur due to the fault of the speaker, or because of the modesty or shyness of the compliment object [10. 202].

As for the English linguistic culture, there is a negative reaction of the interlocutor to a compliment, according to R.V. Serebryakova, much less often, in comparison with Russian linguistic culture [10. 18].

The same point of view is held by a foreign researcher B. Langford, from the point of view of which the English rules of speech etiquette imply a simple and direct response to a

compliment. For example: Thank you. I'm glad the situation turned out well. A negative reaction (for example, Oh, it was no big deal) is not characteristic of the English communicative culture [10. 48].

The English communicative culture is such that the British are not used to arguing with the interlocutor because of false ideas about modesty. However, a negative reaction to a compliment in English linguistic culture does occur with the following errors in compliments:

-an error in choosing the subject of a compliment; inappropriate compliment in this situation; antipathy of the addressee to the speaker; the uncertainty of the object in the sincerity of the compliment [10. 18].

In both Russian and English culture, the most frequent recipient of a compliment is a woman. However, the addressee of a compliment differs in two cultures: in English communication, a compliment is more often used in replicas of women, while in Russian communication a compliment is noticeable for the most part in men's speech. P. Eckert discusses the gender characteristics of the English compliment.

In Russian communication culture, on the contrary, a compliment is more often pronounced by men, because, according to etiquette rules, young girls and women, by virtue of their modesty, cannot compliment in order not to fall into an awkward position. However, the recipient of the compliment, as in English culture, is often the women who act, since, as mentioned above, compliments between men are considered indecent. Thus, a compliment as a component of speech etiquette reveals significant discrepancies in the English and Russian communicative cultures. This is due to the mentality of people of different nationalities, their national character, habits and attitudes characteristic of this community [13].

Thus, although all compliments are evaluative and often pronounced expressive judgments, their real semantics allows us to highlight a number of criteria for their classification. At the same time, speech acts of praise / compliment are implemented in the Russian and English languages in a non-identical way, corresponding to different characteristics of speech acts.

Based on a preliminary analysis of the factual material and the study of theoretical prerequisites for the national character and communicative behavior of Russians and English, we have summarized the above typological criteria, forming a classification of compliments that serves to identify the features of this type of speech acts in two communicative cultures. So, in speech acts of praise / compliment, the national-cultural features of the Russian and English ethnic communities can be expressed:

- in objects of compliments; at its addressees and addressees; in the ways of implementing a compliment; in the language of compliment; in relation to the compliment and reaction to it.

We took these criteria as a basis for the classification of compliment and analysis of general patterns and distinctive features of the implementation of the speech acts we are considering in the English and Russian communicative cultures.

A compliment may evaluate individual traits of a person's character, his appearance and clothing, his internal moral qualities, abilities, and other virtues. The list of potential objects of praise and compliments in both Russian and English communicative culture is quite large, but, of course, a number of objects are the most common in complimentary statements. Our task is to identify these objects and determine the frequency of use of the Russian and English linguistic personality of speech acts with various objects of praise / compliment.

A number of works and studies are devoted to compliment as a rhetorical genre in modern science. Some of them are directly focused on the study of compliment in Russian and English communicative culture, which is most consistent with the purpose of our work. Therefore, we use the best practices in this area to characterize objects of complimentary statements.

It is obvious that in both Russian and English communicative cultures, women are more likely to be both addressees and recipients of compliments. In both cultures, the communicative tactics of female and male compliments are manifested both at the level of choice of topics of utterances, and at the level of choice of language units. In the language of men complimenting women, there is an emotionally-evaluative vocabulary that characterizes the –feminine|| principle, namely tenderness, softness, sophistication, elegance, etc. Similar vocabulary is also used by women in relation to women and men, but compliments of this kind are not frequent and typical in communication between men. Men, making compliments to each other, usually use vocabulary of a different emotional and evaluative tonality, which is characterized by a "masculine" principle: strength, firmness, persuasiveness, and prudence.

In both Russian and English communicative cultures, compliments can directly indicate a person's worth (direct compliments) or indirectly (indirect compliments). We determined the general characteristics of these two types of speech act in Russian and English speech behavior - the general composition of the speech act, a list of objects and existing subspecies of such compliments. As for the compliment-antithesis, based on the material of the studied units, we assume that it is not common in English speech communication, which also, in our opinion, is explained by the etiquette nature of the compliment in the English communicative culture, for which the compliment-antithesis may seem impolite and too familiar.

A Russian linguistic personality, if he shows some kind of verbal reaction to a compliment, then, as a rule, agrees with him, accompanying his consent with a rational motivation for his justice. The native speaker of English is inclined to demonstrate joy, pleasure from the received compliment and gratitude, which we also explain by the emotionality of English communication and the desire to follow the prescribed speech etiquette.

In its most general form, the verbal response to a compliment in both cultures can be expressed by accepting a compliment or disagreement with it. The latter, in turn, can be caused by obvious flattery, irony and ridicule, negative comparisons, the speaker's excessive familiarity, the recipient's uncertainty about the sincerity of the compliment, the antipathy of the addressee to the addresser, or the modesty of the addressee [16].

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion we can say that, in this paper, we analyzed the features of praise / compliment speech acts from the perspective of the theory of speech acts, and also analyzed the object orientation, the compliment vector, implementation methods, and language design of these speech acts in Russian and English communicative cultures.

Thus, from the analysis of factual material, it becomes obvious that the basis of speech acts of praise / compliment is a frame that includes images of the addressee (subject of the compliment), the addressee or a third person who is not in the communicative space, as well as the object (object) of the compliment. In general, the list of objects of speech acts of praise / compliment is quite diverse, but studies conducted in this area allow us to highlight the most typical object orientation of compliments for Russian and English communicative cultures. In communication, Russians mainly pay attention to external factors, which confirms the

productivity in the Russian communicative culture of compliments to the appearance of a person, praise for a job well done. For the British, internal factors play a large role, which is manifested in the frequent use of compliments to the moral qualities and intellectual abilities of man.

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